

April 2023: Top Cited Articles in Ubiquitous Computing (IJU)

**International Journal of Ubiquitous
Computing (IJU)**

ISSN : 0975 - 8992(Online); 0976 - 2213(Print)

<http://www.airccse.org/journal/iju/index.html>

Performance Comparison of Routing Protocols in Mobile Ad Hoc Networks

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ABSTRACT

Routing protocols have an important role in any Mobile Ad Hoc Network (MANET). Researchers have elaborated several routing protocols that possess different performance levels. In this paper we give a performance evaluation of AODV, DSR, DSDV, OLSR and DYMO routing protocols in Mobile Ad Hoc Networks (MANETS) to determine the best in different scenarios. We analyse these MANET routing protocols by using NS-2 simulator. We specify how the Number of Nodes parameter influences their performance. In this study, performance is calculated in terms of Packet Delivery Ratio, Average End to End Delay, Normalised Routing Load and Average Throughput.

KEYWORDS

Mobile Ad Hoc Networks (MANETs), Performance Comparaison, AODV, DSR, DSDV, OLSR, DYMO

Volume URL : <https://www.airccse.org/journal/iju/vol6.html>

Source URL : <https://airccse.org/journal/iju/papers/6215iju01.pdf>

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A proposed Novel Approach for Sentiment Analysis and Opinion Mining

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ABSTRACT

As the people are being dependent on internet the requirement of user view analysis is increasing exponentially. Customer posts their experience and opinion about the product policy and services. But, because of the massive volume of reviews, customers can't read all reviews. In order to solve this problem, a lot of research is being carried out in Opinion Mining. Through the Opinion Mining, we can know about contents of whole product reviews, Blogs are websites that allow one or more individuals to write about things they want to share with other. The valuable data contained in posts from a large number of users across geographic, demographic and cultural boundaries provide a rich data source not only for commercial exploitation but also for psychological & sociopolitical research. This paper tries to demonstrate the plausibility of the idea through our clustering and classifying opinion mining experiment on analysis of blog posts on recent product policy and services reviews. We are proposing a Novel approach for analyzing the Review for the customer opinion.

Volume URL : <https://www.airccse.org/journal/iju/vol5.html>

Source URL : <https://airccse.org/journal/iju/papers/5214iju01.pdf>

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Intelligent Approaches to interact with Machines using Hand Gesture Recognition in Natural way: A Survey

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ABSTRACT

Over the past couple of years, the extent of the services provided on the mobile devices has increased rapidly. A special class of service among them is the Location Based Service(LBS) which depends on the geographical position of the user to provide services to the end users. However, a mobile device is still resource constrained, and some applications usually demand more resources than a mobile device can afford. To alleviate this, a mobile device should get resources from an external source. One of such sources is cloud computing platforms. We can predict that the mobile area will take on a boom with the advent of this new concept. The aim of this paper is to exchange messages between user and location service provider in mobile device accessing the cloud by minimizing cost, data storage and processing power. Our main goal is to provide dynamic location-based service and increase the information retrieve accuracy especially on the limited mobile screen by accessing cloud application. In this paper we present location based restaurant information retrieval system and we have developed our application in Android.

Volume URL : <https://www.airccse.org/journal/iju/vol2.html>

Source URL : <https://airccse.org/journal/iju/papers/2411iju04.pdf>

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Checkpointing with Minimal Recovery in Adhoc Net Based TMR

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ABSTRACT

This paper describes two-fold approach towards utilizing Triple Modular Redundancy (TMR) in Wireless Adhoc Network (AdocNet). A distributed checkpointing and recovery protocol is proposed. The protocol eliminates useless checkpoints and helps in selecting only dependent processes in the concerned checkpointing interval, to recover. A process starts recovery from its last checkpoint only if it finds that it is dependent (directly or indirectly) on the faulty process. The recovery protocol also prevents the occurrence of missing or orphan messages. In AdocNet, a set of three nodes (connected to each other) is considered to form a TMR set, being designated as main, primary and secondary. A main node in one set may serve as primary or secondary in another. Computation is not triplicated, but checkpoint by main is duplicated in its primary so that primary can continue if main fails. Checkpoint by primary is then duplicated in secondary if primary fails too.

KEYWORDS

checkpointing, dependency tracking, rollback recovery, adhoc networks, triple modular redundancy

Volume URL : <https://www.airccse.org/journal/iju/vol6.html>

Source URL : <https://aircconline.com/iju/V6N4/6415iju03.pdf>

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Proximity Based Adaptation of Content to Groups of Viewers of Public Displays

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ABSTRACT

Responsive design adapts web content to different viewing contexts to deliver an optimal viewing and interaction experience. Recent work proposed a model and framework for proximity-based adaptation of web content as a new dimension for responsive web design. While it was shown that the model improves the perception and user engagement for single viewers, until now, the effect had not been investigated for multiple simultaneous viewers who may be at different distances from the display. In this paper, we report on an initial study that evaluated and compared the effects of using the average distance of viewers as the basis for handling adaptation of content to multiple viewers with a classic one that adapts content based only on display characteristics. Our results show that the adaptive model provides a better view of the content and improves user engagement, but can be confusing when serving multiple viewers.

KEYWORDS

Distance; large displays; Responsive design; multiple viewers

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Volume URL : <https://airconline.com/iju/V9N2/9218iju01.pdf>

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A Survey: To Harness an Efficient Energy in Cloud Computing

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ABSTRACT

Cloud computing affords huge potential for dynamism, flexibility and cost-effective IT operations. Cloud computing requires many tasks to be executed by the provided resources to achieve good performance, shortest response time and high utilization of resources. To achieve these challenges there is a need to develop a new energy aware scheduling algorithm that outperform appropriate allocation map of task to optimize energy consumption. This study accomplished with all the existing techniques mainly focus on reducing energy consumption

KEYWORDS

Cloud computing, Energy consumption, Virtualization, renewable energy, Virtual machine

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Volume URL : <https://aircse.org/journal/iju/papers/6315iju01.pdf>

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Analysing the Correlation of Geriatric Assessment Scores and Activity in Smart Homes

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ABSTRACT

A continuous monitoring of the physical strength and mobility of elderly people is important for maintaining their health and treating diseases at an early stage. However, frequent screenings by physicians are exceeding the logistic capacities. An alternate approach is the automatic and unobtrusive collection of functional measures by ambient sensors. In the current publication, we show the correlation among data of ambient motion sensors and the well-established mobility assessments Short-PhysicalPerformance-Battery, Tinetti and Timed Up & Go. We use the average number of motion sensor events as activity measure for correlation with the assessment scores. The evaluation on a real-world dataset shows a moderate to strong correlation with the scores of standardised geriatrics physical assessments.

KEYWORDS

ubiquitous computing, biomedical informatics, health, correlation, piecewise linear approximation

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Lightweight Mobile Web Service Provisioning for the Internet of Things Mediation

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ABSTRACT

Emerging sensor-embedded smartphones motivated the mobile Internet of Things research. With the integrated embedded hardware and software sensor components, and mobile network technologies, smartphones are capable of providing various environmental context information via embedded mobile device-hosted Web services (MWS). MWS enhances the capability of various mobile sensing applications such as mobile crowdsensing, real time mobile health monitoring, mobile social network in proximity and so on. Although recent smartphones are quite capable in terms of mobile data transmission speed and computation power, the frequent usage of high performance multi-core mobile CPU and the high speed 3G/4G mobile Internet data transmission will quickly drain the battery power of the mobile device. Although numerous previous researchers have tried to overcome the resource intensive issues in mobile embedded service provisioning domain, most of the efforts were constrained because of the underlying resource intensive technologies. This paper presents a lightweight mobile Web service provisioning framework for mobile sensing which utilises the protocols that were designed for constrained Internet of Things environment. The prototype experimental results show that the proposed framework can provide higher throughput and less resource consumption than the traditional mobile Web service frameworks.

KEYWORDS

Mobile Web service; CoAP; Lightweight; Cconstrained Service Provider

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Efficient and Secure Authentication and Key Agreement Protocol

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ABSTRACT

In the UMTS Authentication and Key Agreement (AKA) protocol only the home network can generate authentication vectors to its subscribers. Therefore; the home location register and authentication centre (HLR/AuC) actually suffers from the traffic bottleneck. AKA protocol has been enhanced by generating temporary key to enable visitor location register (VLR/SGSN) to authenticate mobile station (MS) without intervention of HLR/AuC. This proposed protocol called Efficient AKA (E-AKA),

The proposed protocol satisfies the security requirements of third generation (3G) mobile networks. In this research paper the current AKA has been enhanced by reducing the network traffic, signalling message between entities. This is achieved by reducing a size n array of authentication vector and the number of messages between MS and HLR/AuC. Hence, the traffic for the home network to generate authentication vectors is exponentially decreased, then reducing the authentication times, and setup time as well as improving authentication efficiency. Additionally, a mutual authentication between MS and its Home Network (HN) and between an MS and the Serving Network (SN) is achieved. A security analysis and comparison with related work shows that E-AKA is more efficient and a secure authentication is achieved.

KEYWORDS

3G, Authentication, Security, Mobile Station, and Authentication Vector

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Secured Smart System Desing in Pervasive Computing Environment Using VCS

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ABSTRACT

Ubiquitous Computing uses mobile phones or tiny devices for application development with sensors embedded in mobile phones. The information generated by these devices is a big task in collection and storage. For further, the data transmission to the intended destination is delay tolerant. In this paper, we made an attempt to propose a new security algorithm for providing security to Pervasive Computing Environment (PCE) system using Public-key Encryption (PKE) algorithm, Biometric Security (BS) algorithm and Visual Cryptography Scheme (VCS) algorithm. In the proposed PCE monitoring system it automates various home appliances using VCS and also provides security against intrusion using Zigbee IEEE 802.15.4 based Sensor Network, GSM and Wi-Fi networks are embedded through a standard Home gateway.

KEYWORDS

GSM, WI-Fi, Zigbee, Context-aware, Smart Sensor, and Pervasive Computing Environment, Public-Key Encryption, Visual Cryptography Scheme and MMS.

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